

THE ROLE AND IMPORTANCE OF TERMS IN LANGUAGE

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Аннотация. В статье излагаются представления о профессиональной лексике – (профессионализмах), словах и понятиях, характерных для речи людей определенной профессии или рода занятий, профессионализмах (профессиональных словах), характерных для других языков и диалектов, и лексике общеупотребительного языка.

Ключевые слова: язык и культура, национальный язык, литературный язык, профессиональная лексика, профессиональная лексика ножеделия, термины, узбекские термины ножеделия, лингвокультурные и лингвоареальные языковые особенности.

Annotation. The article presents ideas about professional vocabulary – (professionalisms), words and concepts characteristic of the speech of people of a certain profession or occupation, professionalisms (professional words) characteristic of other languages and dialects, and the vocabulary of a common language.

Key words: language and culture, national language, literary language, professional vocabulary, professional vocabulary of knifemaking, terms, Uzbek terms of knifemaking, linguacultural and linguaareal linguistic features.

Professional Vocabulary (Professionalisms) refers to the collection of words and concepts specific to the speech of individuals engaged in a particular profession or craft. The primary sources for the formation of professional vocabulary include borrowing words from other languages, dialect-specific words, and words with altered meanings from the common language.

The naming of an object or item differently by people of various professions (e.g., “qozon” – a pot – called “potila” by confectioners) can also give rise to professional vocabulary.

The vocabulary of highly developed professional fields (e.g., cotton farming, medicine, technology, etc.) is rich, with a significant amount of specialized literature published in these areas.

Scientific and technical terms are crucial sources for enriching the overall vocabulary of a language and for studying the history of a people’s material culture.

In fiction, professional vocabulary serves as a literary tool to highlight the characteristics and nature of specific characters more vividly.

As is well known, the Uzbek people have long been engaged in various professions and crafts. Consequently, different branches of professional activity have flourished in every region and district of Uzbekistan. Examples include pottery, embroidery, carpentry, blacksmithing, hunting, animal husbandry, shoemaking, gold embroidery, and more. The specialized terms created and still being created by the Uzbek people during the labor process in various professional fields form a rich layer in the vocabulary of the common language.

Some terms become obsolete and are classified as historical terms, while others acquire new functions and meanings and remain in use.

Professional terms often enter common usage, folklore, and written literature over time. The terms associated with people's professions are a vital source for enriching the lexical composition of both our literary language and dialects.

For instance, many complex modern machines are the result of the evolution of simple technologies created by humanity in ancient times. The doors of small, simple houses from early human society, as well as the doors of modern high-tech products like jet airplanes, advanced cars, or submarines, are all referred to as "door" in our current spoken and literary language.

Similarly, the blades and axles of the potter's wheel or simple water mill, inventions from the era of slavery, and the corresponding parts of modern airplanes, helicopters, or ships are still referred to by the same names. Thus, the elements and names of old technologies often carry over to newer, more advanced forms of technology. Likewise, words and terms created during the labor process have continually enriched the vocabulary of nearly all branches of science.

As colorful products made by professionals enter public consumption and are used by various societal strata, the specialized terms denoting these products become part of common vocabulary. Through repeated use, these terms acquire figurative meanings, serve as the basis for various comparisons, and are incorporated into proverbs, sayings, fixed expressions, and idiomatic phrases, thereby enriching the vocabulary.

For example, the term "needle", which refers to a tool used in sewing, appears in expressions like:

- "From thread to needle" – in full detail, down to the smallest parts.
- "To dig a well with a needle" – an extremely difficult, nearly impossible task.
- "He made a camel out of a needle's mouth." – exaggerated or blown out of proportion.

Similarly, the word "axe" appears in "unspoken word" – a humorous expression meaning a fresh or novel idea. The words "weaver" and "shuttle" are used in "bo'zchining mokisidek" – meaning someone who is constantly on the move. The words "sickle" and "hoe" appear in "He takes the sickle of the one who passed by, and the hoe of the one who left" – describing someone quarrelsome who takes others' tools, or in the modern expression "The hoe flew" – meaning someone got lucky. The word "mill" is used in "If it goes into the mill, it comes out whole" – meaning someone who can find a way out of any difficult situation. The word "iron" appears in "Strike while the iron is hot." – meaning to do something at the right moment, and "blacksmith" is used in "Were your ancestors blacksmiths?" – said to someone who drags out a conversation unnecessarily, likening it to a blacksmith stretching heated iron.

These examples show how terms originally belonging to professional vocabulary, such as "needle," "pierce," "scissor," "shuttle," "iron," "scythe," and "hoe," have become ingrained in our spoken language with figurative meanings and various comparisons.

Sometimes, words in common use are linked by professionals to specific events or phenomena in their professional lives, acquiring specialized meanings. These terms may then re-enter common vocabulary with those specialized meanings.

Another example is the term "gold expert". Originally referring to a specialist who can distinguish the quality of gold (or rare metals in general), in spoken language, it has come to

mean someone who can distinguish good from bad or who has a nuanced perspective on matters. This meaning has also entered literary language.

Some words in the core vocabulary of common usage may become specialized terms in professional vocabulary, denoting specific objects or concepts, and then re-enter the language with those meanings. An example is the word “pain” in shoemaking. Shoemakers insert small pieces of leather between the heel or sole and the upper part of a shoe to produce a squeaking sound when walking on the ground. This piece is called “g’arch,” and the shoe is referred to as “squeaky shoe”. This term has moved from the shoemakers’ vocabulary into spoken language and literary language. For instance, the poet Zavqi used this word in this sense in his poetry:

Wealth, honor, and glory belong to the brave,
In this era, the smooth turbaned one wears squeaky shoes.

Here, the poet uses “wearing squeaky shoes” to refer to wealthy merchants or traders, reflecting the class dynamics of his time. The same word appears in the works of Hamza Hakimzoda Niyoz:

“Low-heeled American boots, squeaky shoes like a song, attract all the grudges of the earth, dear aunt.”

Today, this meaning of “pain” has become part of the core vocabulary. Similarly, the word “file” is used figuratively to describe someone irritating or nerve-wracking: “Have you become so annoying?” or “He’s so irritating!” .

Both oral traditions, dialects, and written literature have always enriched their vocabulary through words and terms related to various professions. In the past and present, writers and poets have extensively used professional terms in their works. This occurs because their works connect ideas, events, and phenomena to social life and labor, depicting production scenes and giving voice to characters.

The widespread use of profession-related terms in dialects, oral literature, and common vocabulary results in their integration into the core vocabulary of a language.

One term of the tools that expresses the national identity and unique traditions of a people is the term. Terms have been studied in various languages, and in Uzbek linguistics, they have also been studied as objects of research. Academic Sh. Shoabdurahmonov emphasized the critical need to compile and scientifically study the Uzbek vocabulary, stating:

“If the traditional Uzbek lexicon is not fully documented in the near future, it can be said, with all responsibility, that as the older generation passes away, a significant portion of the valuable linguistic material preserved in their memory and passed down to us may be lost forever.” .

The first to collect a professional lexicon in the Uzbek language was the famous linguist S. Ibrohimov. He collected and linguistically analyzed professional terms in the Fergana dialect, which are disappearing from our lives and have not yet been studied by anyone, and compiled a dictionary of such words .

A.Sobirov, recognizing the merits of this scientist, presents the following sentences: “The merits of Professor S.Ibrahimov in the formation and development of professional lexicon are incomparable. The scientist collected about 2,500 lexical units from the lexicon of silk workers, tandir makers, wormers, degressors, rightagars, metalworkers, blacksmiths, locksmiths, needleworkers, knifemakers, locksmiths, farriers, farriers, coppersmiths, anjomasonry, nailmakers, chainmakers, painters, jewelers, nailmakers, merchants, and

gahchilars and conducted research on them. As a result, his works served as a valuable source for many subsequent works. In the 60s-90s, the role of the professional lexicological school founded by S.Ibrahimov in educating and bringing up a whole generation of terminologists and lexicologists was incomparably great” .

It is clear from this that it is appropriate to study professional vocabulary in connection with people's work and daily activities. Since people's professional activities are an integral part of human life, it is necessary to study them taking into account customs, values, and traditions.

Professional vocabulary, like terms, is one of the special units of the language. Professional vocabulary is special units used within a specific profession and related to it. In each language, words related to professional areas that are directly related to people's life and livelihood are diverse and are considered active lexical layers in terms of their use. Terminology involves the terminization of words and, conversely, the determination of terms. Both professional vocabulary and terms are part of the special lexicon. The professional lexicon has the following properties in the status of a term:

1. Professional terms are also included in the terminological system and are its components.

2. Within the terminological system, professional terms have a gender-species (hyperhyponymic) and whole-part (paronymic holo-meronymic) relationship:

a) the term hyperonym is used in relation to the head word, the dominant, which expresses a general meaning in relation to certain types and occurs in the core (center) of the semantic field. This word indicates gender. For example, if the names of objects and weapons used in pottery generally indicate gender, then each object used (bowl, paella, plate, jug) indicates its type. In this case, we can see a secondary gender-species relationship.

For example, if a type of object used in pottery is considered a weapon, then various jugs used in pottery (such as a qoshquloqcha (Tashkent), khurmacha (Tashkent), kokanak (Rishton), chapiya (Rishton), water jug (Rishton), balbala) indicate relative gender.

In this field: the hyperonym tavoq combines hyponyms such as charkh tavoq (Rishton), tavoqi langari (Samarkand), naqshin tavoq (Gijduvan), lali tavoq (Samarkand), pikpin tavoq (Rishton), miyona tavoq (Gijduvan), maraka tavoq, langari tavoq, toy tavoq, nim tavoq, kharchagi tavoq, bas tavoq, etc.

In pottery, the terms pattern are hyperonyms, such as cinnimuhr, shamdoni hashtag, yalpizgul, aftobi, pirpiraq topmunchaq, girdobi parra, palakgul, shabaki, chig'iriy, davrai khurshid, hashti havzagi, chormag'iz, kara ilon, mori siyeh, etc. are geponyms;

b) whole-part (paronymic holo-meronymic) relationship. For example, in the field of pottery, the whole name ketnak enters into a paronymic relationship with units denoting part names such as lid, spout, stem. Or, the whole name charkh gildraq enters into a paronymic relationship with units denoting part names such as kizil gildraq kizil gildraq kizil gildraq oq, yog oq.

The difference between paronymy and hyperhyponymy is that in hyponymy, one part (member) of the field is contrasted with others and the semantic relations between them are determined, while in paronymy, the issue of the relationship of the part (member) taken separately with the internal organs that make it up is raised.

3. In terms of structure, like other terms, there are simple, compound and complex (linguoterminologically, i.e. terms equivalent to word combinations). For example, a) Simple

words: embroidery, large jug, potter, shoemaker, plate, clay, mud, clay (raw), porcelain, jug, small jug, large flat dish, drum, tray, ceramics, tile, tile maker, potter (jug maker), tandoor oven maker

b) Compound words: pomegranate flower, almond flower, pepper flower, marigold, cornflower, double line, triple line, quadruple line, intricate pattern, sparrow wing, crow's claw, cherry leaf.

c) Composite terms: lattice-like pattern, rhombus-like pattern, triangular shape, triangular pattern, circular shape, circular pattern, chain-like pattern, chain-like shape, dotted pattern, black checkered pattern, white checkered pattern, curved line, straight line, small circular pattern.

4. The composition may contain words from other languages. For example, in the field of pottery, Persian-Tajik terms include: Roman band, gajaq leaf, circle, sun circle, dentate, date tree, ring, two-gajaq pearl, two curved lines, fish tail, comb chain, spring chain, golden base. Arabic terms include: phoenix, house, large, earner, draft, pearl, carved, patchwork, monument, collar, design, noble, condition, pattern, Chinese pattern, decorator, Chinese decorator, painter.

Arabic-Persian terms Two-component terms are also found in the terminology of pottery. Such terms were created in other languages and in this form migrated to the Uzbek language. Such terms in the terminology of the field consist of Arabic-Persian terms. These include the following: naqshband, naqshbandlig, naqshbin, naqshgir, naqshpayvand (painter), naqshsoz, raqamkor (drawn), akhzarvash (green top), akhzargun, juradon (water vessel), lalgun (red), lalfam, sahargun (white color), shafaqvash (red as dawn), shafaqgun, hirfavvar (craftsman).

4. Terms borrowed from other languages In the vocabulary of ceramics, words borrowed from other foreign languages are in the last place in terms of their importance. Therefore, we will limit ourselves to giving a general list of units borrowed from Russian and other foreign languages: ceramics (Greek), porcelain, tiles, alfresco, incrustation (Russian), koler, composition, capital, medallion (Latin), kompanovka, scale, layout, material, ornament, palmette, rhythm, ruta, stylization, silhouette, symmetry, scalpel, smalta, frieze, faience (Italian), abrasive (Latin), gouache (Italian), gurunt (German), self-portrait (French), alizarin (French), amalgam (Lat.), amphora (Lat.), anthracite (Greek), etc.

5. Affixation is an active method in the formation of professional terms. Most of the word-forming suffixes existing within the general Uzbek language participate in the formation of words and terms of this lexicon. The most important of these suffixes are: -chi, -gir, -xona, -kash, -kor, -don, -liq -chiliq -li, -simon, -soz, -furush, -shunos, -paz, -xo`r, -boz, etc. We observe the formation of various words and terms related to the vocabulary of pottery using these suffixes.

For example: the affix -chi not only indicates a person belonging to a certain field of activity, but also indicates that he is engaged in this profession: boyok+chi, naqsh+chi, rasm+chi, tandir+chi, khumdon+chi, charx+chi, haykal+chi, chega+chi, such as; tekstil+soz, chinni+soz, charx+soz.

Some linguists express an opinion that the units of the professional lexicon denote objects and phenomena of the past related to the profession. In particular, S. Usmanov describes the professional lexicon as follows: "The professional lexicon consists not of objects that are the main direction and type of production in modern life, but of the names of the

scattered and weak production tools and production processes of the forgotten or forgotten past, which are lagging behind the current industrial capabilities” .

In our opinion, the professional lexicon is not a set of words that have already become historical or are being forgotten, but rather, they are developing, updated, and modern production terms.

In short, if the term and professional lexicon are united into a single whole with integral signs, they form separate features with differential signs. They have a tendency to strive for monosemiotics within a certain field of science and profession, and serve to clearly express an object or phenomenon in the scientific or production sphere.

Currently, Uzbek terminology is developing in all directions with rapid steps. The basic concepts of science, science and technology, politics, economics, and cultural life are provided with a balanced terminology system.

During the years of independence, a variety of bilingual, multilingual, and explanatory dictionaries have appeared in the country. Currently, intensive work is being carried out on the compilation of terminological dictionaries in various fields, educational, educational-methodical and scientific literature on terminology is being published. The role of the mass media in the further development of Uzbek terminology is becoming significant.

It is a fact that the main source of enrichment, completion and improvement of a specific terminological system of the current Uzbek literary language, as in other languages, is undoubtedly its own vocabulary.

The development of Uzbek terminology at the expense of its own resources and capabilities occurs in two ways:

a) using ready-made words available in the language to express new objects and concepts;

b) creating new terms with the participation of the word-formation capabilities of the Uzbek literary language. In the implementation of new terms, morphological, semantic and syntactic methods of word formation are effectively used.

The method of coinage also plays a significant role in the creation of terms. A huge share of the terminology of the Uzbek language is made up of names that arose on the basis of the Russian-international fund. Terms adopted from other non-Turkic languages are characterized by the fact that they cover the social, political, economic, cultural, and spiritual aspects of the activities of the Uzbek people. The adoption of the Law “On the State Language” by the Supreme Council of Uzbekistan on October 21, 1989 required a new approach to the terminological lexicon, which is considered one of the main layers of the vocabulary of the Uzbek language.

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